

Better Economics for the Earth: A Thought-Provoking Exploration of Economics and the Universe

Amazon Book Review Series of “*Better Economics for the Earth: A Lesson from Quantum and Information Theories*”

Vdeva & Shantiananda

November 26, 2024

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A Thought-Provoking Exploration of Economics and the Universe

The most captivating aspect of this book is its bold challenge to the human-centric worldview that dominates economics. By stepping back and considering humanity’s place in the vast universe, the author prompts readers to question long-standing assumptions and principles that have shaped our economic systems. This shift in perspective feels both humbling and necessary, especially as we grapple with pressing issues like climate change and the rise of AI.

Vdeva

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Reviewed in the United States on November 26, 2024

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The discussion of value is particularly fascinating. By integrating concepts from quantum mechanics and information theory, the book offers a fresh lens for understanding how value operates in dynamic and interconnected systems. It's a complex topic, but the writing is clear and accessible, making it an engaging read even for those without a deep background in physics or economics.

Screenshot. Review of “*Better Economics for the Earth*” by Vdeva [1]. Reviewed in the United States on November 26, 2024.

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Redefining Economics: Lessons from Physics for a Sustainable Future

I found this to be a thought-provoking book. Not only does it challenge traditional economic paradigms, it urges economists to draw insights from physics, particularly quantum and information theories. It argues for a shift away from human-centered thinking toward a more

universal perspective, recognizing Earth as a unique and fragile habitat. The authors propose a new definition of value, aiming to address modern challenges like environmental crises and AI more effectively. I think it blends interdisciplinary knowledge, to pave the way for a more adaptable and forward-thinking approach to economics. It makes a compelling read for anyone interested in the intersection of science and social systems.

Shantiananda

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Screenshot. Review of “*Better Economics for the Earth*” by Shantiananda [2]. Reviewed in the United States on November 27, 2024.

(*) Note: This paper reprints Vdeva’s and Shantiananda’s reviews [1,2] appearing on the Amazon page of the title [3].

References

- [1] Vdeva. (2024, Nov. 26). A Thought-Provoking Exploration of Economics and the Universe. <https://www.amazon.com/gp/customer-reviews/RRF2WUSY7Q1PN/>
- [2] Shantiananda. (2024, Nov. 27). Redefining Economics: Lessons from Physics for a Sustainable Future. <https://www.amazon.com/gp/customer-reviews/R47IF1IOG0ACL/>
- [3] Vuong, Q. H. & Nguyen, M. H. (2024). *Better Economics for the Earth: A Lesson from Quantum and Information Theories*. <https://www.amazon.com/dp/BOD98L5K44>